

Polarization-independent metasurfaces based on bound states in the continuum with high Q-factor and resonance modulation

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Abstract: Metasurfaces offer a powerful platform for effective light manipulation, which is crucial for advanced optical technologies. While designs of polarization-independent structures have reduced the need for polarized illumination, they are often limited by either low Q factors or low resonance modulation. Here, we design and experimentally demonstrate a metasurface with polarization-independent quasi-bound state in the continuum (quasi-BIC), where the unit cell consists of four silicon squares arranged in a two-dimensional array and the resonance properties can be controlled by adjusting the edge length difference between different squares. Our metasurface experimentally achieves a Q factor of approximately 100 and a resonance modulation of around 50%. This work addresses a common limitation in previous designs, which either achieved high Q factors exceeding 200 with a resonance modulation of less than 10%, leading to challenging signal-to-noise ratio requirements, or achieved strong resonance modulation with Q factors of only around 10, limiting light confinement and fine-tuning capabilities. In contrast, our metasurface ensures that the polarization-independent signal is sharp and distinct within the system, reducing the demands on signal-to-noise ratio and improving robustness. Experiments show the consistent performance across different polarization angles. This work contributes to the development of versatile optical devices, enhancing the potential for the practical application of BIC-based designs in areas such as optical filtering and sensing.

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1. Introduction

Metasurfaces represent a significant step forward in optical manipulation [1,2]. Traditionally, optical control has relied on bulky lenses and components, however, the advent of metasurfaces has revolutionized this field. With their subwavelength thickness and the use of engineered nanostructures, they allow for precise control over the phase, amplitude, and polarization of light [3,4]. This transition from conventional to flat optics offers distinct advantages, such as compactness, flexibility, and the potential for on-chip integration, expanding the possibilities of optical devices [5–8].

In the field of metasurfaces, the concept of symmetry-protected bound states in the continuum (BIC) has emerged as a powerful tool for manipulating light [9–12]. They provide a unique mechanism for manipulating light, offering high-quality resonances that can be leveraged in various optical applications such as strong coupling, sensing and optical filtering [13–18]. However, most quasi-BIC designs and applications are polarization-dependent, which limits their efficiency in applications where the incident beam is unpolarized. For instance, in sensing and filtering scenarios with unpolarized light sources, polarization-dependent designs waste nearly half of the incident light energy or impose strict conditions on the polarization of incident light [17,19–21]. This inefficiency highlights the need for polarization-independent quasi-BIC designs,

which can more effectively harness light across all polarization states, thereby facilitating the transition from academic research to industrial applications.

Currently, there are two prominent approaches to design polarization-independent quasi-BIC resonances. The first approach places the resonators supporting the quasi-BIC mode in a circular arrangement to obtain polarization invariance and large quality factors (Q factors) exceeding 200 [17]. However, these metasurface designs typically exhibit a resonance modulation of only around 10% and face challenges related to their innately low filling factors. Consequently, such radial structures can produce low signal-to-noise ratios in sensing experiments, leading to issues for molecular differentiation. Likewise, their low total absorption compared to 2D arrays may limit their efficiency in harnessing light source energy, e.g., for energy conversion applications.

The most widely used approach for obtaining polarization independence in quasi-BIC systems is based on C4 symmetric metasurfaces [19–26]. Such C4 symmetric structures exhibit polarization invariance due to their four-fold rotational symmetry, ensuring identical responses to all incident polarization states. However, so far, many experimental realizations of polarization-independent quasi-BIC metasurfaces have either focused on obtaining large resonance modulations at the cost of Q factor in the terahertz band [27,28], or have provided generally low resonance modulations, especially when operated in the more fabricationally challenging visible spectrum [19].

In this work, we present an approach based on C4 symmetry for achieving a polarization-independent metasurface by simply altering the length difference of square elements within the unit cell. This alters the structural periodicity and result in Brillouin zone folding, which changes the distribution of photonic modes in the momentum space, converting a BIC into a quasi-BIC at Γ point [19,29]. In this way, we realize a quasi-BIC metasurface that simultaneously achieves a high experimental Q factor of approximately 100 and a resonance modulation of around 50%. Our design strikes a balance between Q factor and resonance modulation. The high Q factor offers strong field confinement, making it highly sensitive to the surrounding environment. The strong resonance modulation allows the metasurface to respond effectively to external changes like refractive index without being subjected to noise or minor fluctuations. This well-balanced performance suggests that the resonator could be suitable for applications such as sensors, modulators, or filters, where sensitivity and stability against loss or noise are both essential.

2. Results

2.1. Numerical design

Initially, we identified a suitable structure through simulations that achieves the quasi-BIC resonance within the wavelength range accessible for subsequent experimental characterization using CST Studio Suite (Simulia). A three dimensional (3D) illustration of the metasurface is shown in Fig. 1(a), where Si-based resonators are positioned on a silica substrate. Each unit cell has periodicities of $P_x = P_y = 430$ nm and comprises four rectangular blocks, all of which are square-shaped in the top view (Fig. 1(b)). In the BIC configuration, these blocks have identical side lengths, denoted as $A_1 = 185$ nm, as indicated by the dashed lines. To achieve the quasi-BIC resonance, we reduce the side lengths of three squares to A_2 , thereby introducing an in-plane perturbation, leading to a Brillouin zone folding, which transform the nonradiative BIC into a quasi-BIC mode. Meanwhile the whole metasurface retains C4 symmetry, making the resonance polarization-independent. The perturbation parameter dL represents the difference $dL = A_1 - A_2$, and its range is set from 0 nm to 30 nm. Building on this, we can scale the size of dL by multiplying it with a scaling factor $\Delta L = dL \times S$, which is the final length difference at different scaling parameters. The scaling factor S is introduced to uniformly adjust the size of the structure in the xy -plane. When the scaling factor S is adjusted, it is applied to multiple structural parameters, including the periods P_x and P_y , as well as the dimensions A_1 , A_2 , and dL , ensuring that the structure in the xy -plane scales uniformly. The resonator height is fixed at 80 nm. Here,

for example in Fig. 1(c), the scaling factor S is 0.9, meaning the actual length difference, as shown in Fig. 1(b), is calculated as $\Delta L = dL \times 0.9$. For the sake of convenient parameter comparison, we use dL for labeling in the figures and the text. At the same time, we provide the corresponding S values to ensure rigor and clarity. The same way is applied in the subsequent sections as well.

Fig. 1. (a) Three-dimensional schematic of the metasurface, showing the Si-based resonators placed on a silica substrate. (b) Top-view of the unit cell structure, with square-shaped elements having dimensions $P_x = P_y = 430$ nm. The squares are initially identical with side length $A_1 = 185$ nm. To achieve the quasi-BIC resonance, the side lengths of three squares are reduced to A_2 , which is smaller than A_1 . (c) Simulated transmittance spectra of the metasurface for varying dL showing the broadening of the resonance peak with increasing length difference. S is set to 0.9. (d) Simulated spectra as a function of the scaling factor S with $dL = 30$ nm, demonstrating resonance shift across the spectrum by adjusting the structure size.

By introducing dL we change metasurface period from $P_x/2$ to P_x . First, We introduce the perturbation of length difference and obtain the quasi-BIC resonance (Fig. 1(c)). Here clearly illustrate the characteristics of the quasi-BIC: S is set to 0.9. As dL increases, more energy couples into the radiation channel, resulting in a broader linewidth; With dL fixed at 30 nm, adjusting Scaling factor allows us for flexible tuning of the resonance position in the spectrum (Fig. 1(d)). These simulations in Fig. 1 successfully demonstrate the desired quasi-BIC resonance.

Next step is to analyze our quasi-BIC resonance. We clearly observe how BIC (red dashed circle) turns out into quasi-BIC when changing perturbation parameter dL . Transmittance spectra for $S = 1$ and dL varying from -10 to 30 nm are simulated (Fig. 2(a)). An additional resonance feature can be observed at a wavelength of 675 nm. However, due to its weak amplitude and spectral separation from the main BIC resonance, we will not focus on this mode in our subsequent analysis. For the resonance peak with the greater modulation, we extracted the Q factor for each dL using temporal coupled-mode theory (TCMT) [14,30,31], as shown in Fig. 2(b). The corresponding equations are provided in Supplement 1. The Q factor exhibits an inverse square relationship with the perturbation parameter dL , according to the general rule of quasi-BIC resonance (Fig. 2(b)) [9]. We then select a representative resonance peak at $dL = 20$ nm for further analysis (marked by the red star shape in Fig. 2(a)), performing a multipolar expansion with the incident light polarized in the x-direction (Supplement 1, Fig. S1) [32–35]. We can also choose other parameters, since this doesn't influence the following analysis. The expansion of coupling

parameter includes electric dipole, magnetic dipole, electric quadrupole, magnetic quadrupole, and electric octupole moments. By evaluating each term of the expansion we revealed, that the magnetic quadrupole contributes predominantly, which is consistent with the simulation from previous work [20]. Last, electric field distribution in the xy -plane and the field enhancement factor are analyzed for the representative resonance (marked by the red star shape in Fig. 2(a)). The analysis reveals an enhancement exceeding 30 times, indicating the structure's potential for sensing applications (Fig. 2(c)). The direction of the electric field of the upper and lower parts are in different directions. Due to the introduction of in plane perturbation of the adjacent length difference of the squares, they can no longer compensate each other, resulting in a quasi-BIC resonance accessible from the far field.

Fig. 2. (a) Simulated transmittance spectra for $S = 1$ with dL varying from -10 to 30 nm. (b) Q factor of the resonance peak as a function of dL , showing the characteristic inverse square relationship with dL . (c) Electric field distribution in the xy -plane at the middle cut of the bricks, illustrating the field distribution and enhancement, corresponding to the qBIC resonance with $S = 1$ and $dL = 20$ nm marked by red star shape in Fig. 2(a).

2.2. Experimental realization

We fabricated the designed nanostructures using a top-down approach with E-beam lithography (for details see Fabrication in Supplement 1) and characterized the fabrication results, transmittance spectra, and Q factors. The fabricated structure with $dL = 30$ nm and $S = 0.9$ was under SEM imaged, where the expected structure is clearly shown at Fig. 3(a). Detailed fabrication methods are provided in Supplement 1. We measured the transmittance spectra for dL ranging from 0 to 30 nm with $S = 0.9$. As the dL increase, the transmittance exhibits a spectral shift similar to that observed in simulations (Fig. 1(c) and Fig. 3(b)). We noticed that, in the experiment, two additional resonances with smaller amplitudes appeared on either side of the resonance peak we focused on. This is caused by a slight deviation of incident angle within our experimental setup, which we will explain in the next section. We focused on the second resonance peak from the right in the spectrum, as its resonance modulation varies significantly with changes in dL .

When the scaling factor is adjusted from 0.9 to 1.05 , the structure enlarges, and the transmittance dip red shifts (Fig. 3(c)), which also aligns with the simulation trends. Consequently, we successfully fabricated a metasurface with $C4$ symmetry, and the experimental results are consistent with the simulations. Additionally, using the TCMT model, we extracted the Q factor and resonance modulation for the resonance peak as $S = 0.9$ and dL varied from 10 to 30 nm. Theoretically, the Q factor should become higher at $dL = 10$ nm, but due to influences from fabrication-induced variations in resonator geometry and surface roughness, further enhancement of the Q factor was limited, stabilizing at around 100 . At $dL = 20$ nm, the Q factor reached 110 , with a resonance modulation exceeding 40% . As dL increased further, the Q factor decreased, consistent with the trend in simulation (Fig. 3(d)).

Fig. 3. (a) Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) image of the fabricated metasurface structure with $S = 0.9$ and $dL = 30$ nm. (b) Experimental transmittance spectra for $S = 0.9$ and dL ranging from 0 to 30 nm. (c) Experimental transmittance spectra for $dL = 30$ nm varying scaling factors S from 0.9 to 1.05, demonstrating the redshift of the resonance as the structure size increases, consistent with simulation results. (d) Q factors and corresponding resonance modulations for resonances with $S = 0.9$ and dL varies from 10 to 30 nm.

Intriguingly, we observe that in addition to the resonance of interest, two small additional resonance appeared on either side, which were not present in the simulation results. Through simulations, we determined that this was caused by partial oblique incidence of light during the experiment. We simulated transmittance spectra of TE and TM modes, incident at the angles ranging from -5° to $+5^\circ$ with $S = 1$ and $dL = 20$ nm. The TM mode under oblique incidence leads to a continuous redshift of the resonance peak at 660 nm (Fig. 4(b)). In the experiment, this continuous shift results in the broadening of the resonance peak. For the TE mode, under oblique

Fig. 4. Transmittance spectra of oblique incident TE (a) and TM (b) polarized plane waves for polarization independent quasi-BIC metasurface with $S = 1$ and $dL = 20$ nm. The continuous redshift of the resonance peak at 660 nm and its broadening are observed for TM-polarized oblique incident waves. Oblique incidence of the TE-polarized light leads to revealing two off- Γ quasi-BIC modes on either side of the main peak at 740 nm.

incidence, new quasi-BIC modes are introduced off the Γ -point, appearing on either side of the main spectral peak at 740 nm. (Fig. 4(a)) [36,37]. The combined spectrum of TE and TM modes under oblique incidence cause the mode at 660 nm to broaden and introduce two new quasi-BIC modes around 720 and 760 nm, which are located on either side of the main peak at 740 nm.

2.3. Polarization independence measurements

Following our numerical and experimental analysis, we conducted polarization-dependent measurements. We selected a metasurface with a geometry of $S = 0.9$ and $dL = 30$ nm, corresponding to the $S = 0.9$ curve in Fig. 3(c). Alternatively, any other experimental spectrum could have been chosen, this particular one only serves as a demonstration of polarization-independent results. We measured the spectra with the polarization angle ranging from 0° to 90° , in 15° increments, as well as the spectrum without a polarizer. The resulting spectra are shown in Fig. 5(a). First, we observe that under different polarization angles, the resonance peak remained fixed around 670 nm, with consistent linewidth and resonance modulation, indicating that both the resonance modulation and Q factor remained stable when polarization changes. The resonance frequency shows a slight shift of around 5 nm between 0° and 90° , which may be attributed to fabrication imperfections. However, a more possible factor contributing to this shift is the potential oblique incidence during the measurement process, as discussed in Supplement 1. The Q factors of the measured spectra with different polarization angle are extracted and shown in Fig. 5(b). We can see a stable Q factor along different polarization angles. Then we extracted the Q factor and resonance modulation with and without the polarizer (Fig. 5(c)). The Q factors range between 70 and 80, with a resonance modulation of approximately 60%. Similarly, depending on specific requirements, we can also select an experimental curve with $dL = 20$ nm, where the Q factor is around 110 and the resonance modulation is approximately 40%. This suggests that our polarization-independent resonance exhibits a high Q factor, indicating good light confinement, and a distinct resonance modulation, offering a better signal-to-noise ratio. Such characteristics could be practically effective in applications like filtering and sensing. Additionally, removing the polarizer allows us to utilize energy from both x- and y-polarized light, thereby improving the ability to efficiently capture the energy incident on the device.

Fig. 5. (a) Experimental transmittance spectra of the metasurface with geometry $S = 0.9$ and $dL = 30$ nm, measured for polarization angles from 0° to 90° in 15° increments, along with the spectrum without a polarizer. (b) Q factors extracted from the spectra of different polarization angles. (c) Comparison of Q factor and resonance modulation with and without the polarizer, showing a Q factor between 70 and 80 and a resonance modulation of approximately 60%, highlighting the high Q-factor and strong resonance modulation of the polarization-independent resonance.

3. Conclusion

In summary, we have demonstrated a polarization-independent quasi-BIC metasurface based on C4 symmetry, achieved by altering the edge length difference of square elements within the unit cell. The fabricated metasurface exhibits an experimental Q factor of around 100 and a resonance modulation of around 50%. This advantageous combination of large Q factor and strong resonance modulation allows the resonator to effectively enhance and probe processes occurring in the vicinity of the resonators, which is especially important for optical biosensing, where the maximum sensitivity is constrained by the experimental signal-to-noise level. The fabrication and experimental characterization of the metasurface align well with simulation results. The polarization-independent resonance allows for efficient use of light across different polarization states, which could be beneficial in improving capture efficiency when the incident light is unpolarized. Our work advances the development of polarization-independent quasi-BIC metasurfaces mainly towards their ability for applications where both sensitivity and stability are critical, such as in sensors, modulators, or optical filters.

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Data availability. Data underlying the results presented in this paper are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Supplemental document. See [Supplement 1](#) for supporting content.

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